

GOVERNING GLOBAL CRISES: A LEGAL ANALYSIS OF INTEGRATING DISASTER LAW INTO THE PANDEMIC TREATY

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines how principles from the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction can support the design and implementation of the newly finalized Pandemic Agreement, with a focus on the broader challenge of governing global crises. Although the paper was written before the release of the final Agreement in 2024 and 2025, its analysis of the earlier negotiation drafts remains relevant. Many of the legal and political issues identified during the drafting process, including equity, sovereignty, and international cooperation, continue to shape how states will interpret and apply the Agreement in future crises. The paper first outlines the Sendai Framework's key contributions to disaster governance, including its multi-hazard approach, emphasis on multistakeholder coordination, and focus on international support. It then examines how the Framework integrates health and biological hazards into its priorities and targets. The analysis compares the Sendai Framework and the pandemic treaty process across three areas, namely scope, goals, and guiding principles. It also evaluates the cooperation mechanisms that support the Sendai Framework and considers how these mechanisms relate to the Pandemic Agreement. By identifying areas of alignment and divergence, the paper contributes to ongoing discussions on global health resilience and provides insight into the legal and political dimensions of governing global crises.

Keywords: *Global Health Governance, International Disaster Law, Pandemic Treaty, Sendai Framework.*